

In silico and *invitro* investigation of phytochemical compounds as Janus Kinase inhibitors for asthma

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Abstract

JAK-STAT signalling pathway is a promising target for the drug designing venture for asthma, one of the adverse conditions of the lungs. Phytochemicals including flavonoids are highly recommended for the treatment of asthma. The present study has checked the inhibitory response of flavonoids including phytochemical compounds towards the JAK-STAT signalling pathway. The multi-targeted nature of the ailment has compelled the researchers to think of the potential effect and multi-targeted accessibility of phytochemical compounds, which is more endorse over the present leading medicines including corticosteroids. The less toxic nature of phytochemical compounds is also a highlighting feature. Both *in silico* and *invitro* studies in the present work have explored the potential impact of phytochemical compounds cyanidin, ellagic acid and quercetin as very good JAK inhibitors. Therefore, through the present study, we recommend these phyto molecules from the flavonoid family as very good promising lead systems for asthma.

Key words: Asthma, JAK-STAT pathway, phytochemicals, molecular docking, binding energy analyses, invitro assay.

Introduction

Asthma is a chronic obstructive pulmonary disorder. Advancements in the field of treatment have accrued by the implementation of medicines including inhaled corticosteroids, beta-adrenergic agonists, leukotriene modifiers, mast cell stabilizers etc. along with bronchodilators[1], [2]. Overexpression of interleukin-4 followed by the activation of JAK1 and JAK3 enzymes is a potential causative for asthma[3]. The multi-targeted nature of the disease is also a big problem during drug development[4], [5]. Around 300 million people still are suffering from the condition and the number becomes increasing day by day. The

existing FDA approved JAK1 inhibitors include ruxolitinib, tofacitinib, baricitinib etc which results in thrombocytopenia, neutropenia, fatigue, nausea etc[6]:[7]. Phytochemical compounds are promising candidates with very good therapeutical potential towards most types of diseases including life-threatening ailments[8]:[9]. The main advantages of these candidates are their high therapeutic potential and low rate of toxicity. Phytotherapy is a highly popular technique nowadays[10], [11]. The information on most of today's popular medicines has been collected from the phytochemical world[12]. For each and every problem, there will be an adequate solution in nature. Flavonoids are very good inhibitors of interleukin-4 driven JAK-STAT pathway[13]. The present study is aiming at therapeutic potential of some anti-inflammatory phytochemical compounds including flavonoids against chronic asthma[14].

The present study comprised of *in silico* molecular docking studies of anti-inflammatory phytochemicals with JAK family enzymes including JAK1, JAK2, JAK3 and TYK2. The most responsive phytochemical compounds with JAK1 and JAK3 inhibitory property were found out by the *in silico* studies and their behavior towards JAK1 was established through *in vitro* means.

Materials and methods

In silico studies

Protein preparation

Crystal structures of Janus kinase enzymes including JAK1 (3EYG, 1.9Å), JAK2 (3FUP, 2.4Å), JAK3 (3LXK, 2Å) and TYK2 (3LXN, 2.5Å), were retrieved from the RCSB protein databank [15]. All the structures are co-crystallized with their natural ligand. Protein preparation and optimization were done in the protein preparation wizard of Schrodinger 2015-1 software[16]. Protein optimization followed by minimization was executed at a force field of OPLS_2005 at pH 7.4.

Ligand selection and preparation

A set of 500 anti-inflammatory phytochemical molecules from Dr. Dukes ethnobotanical phytochemical database were taken for the docking studies[17]. Phytochemical molecules include andrographolide, quercetin, curcumin, ellagic acid, cyanidin, piperine, apocynin and resveratrol [14]. Structures of these molecules were drawn, minimized their energy and optimized using 2D sketcher drawing interface and Lig-prep module of the software, Schrodinger 2015-1[18]. The co-crystallized ligand (tofacitinib, approved drug) of all the above-mentioned proteins was same and was considered as

reference compound for interpreting the behaviour of phytochemical molecules with the proteins.

Molecular docking analyses

All the phytochemical molecules were docked with the JAK isozymes including JAK1, JAK2, JAK3 and TYK2 enzymes. The active site of all the proteins was identified by the presence of co-crystal ligand in their respective X-ray crystal structure[19]. Glide module of Schrodinger software 2015-1 was used for molecular docking studies[20]. During the process, van der Waal radius scaling factor was set as 1.0 and partial charge cut off was selected as 0.25. Grid boxes of default dimensions were generated around the active site of each protein. High throughput virtual screening methods were used to find potent phytochemicals obtained from Dr.Dukes ethnobotanical phytochemical database. Flexible docking was executed by extra precision mode of analyses. All the possible poses of ligands were subjected to docking analyses with the proteins and best pose was selected on the basis of its high interaction energies.

Binding energy analyses

The feasibility of molecular docking was assigned by binding energy calculations. Prime MM-GBSA post docking scoring protocol has been carried out for the respective calculation. The docked set of target- ligand complex was imported in the prime module and binding free energies were derived from the system. OPLS-2005force field was applied and water solvent system was selected. Binding energy can be calculated by the equation,

$$G_{\text{bind}} = E_{\text{MM}} + G_{\text{solv}} + G_{\text{SA}} \quad (1)$$

Where EMM - difference in energies of docked system and sum of energies of target and ligand independently, G_{solv} is the difference in solvation energies of docked complex and sum of solvation energies of ligand and un ligated target system and GSA is the difference in energies of surface area of complex and sum of energies of ligand and unligated protein.

Structure based pharmacophore generation

Energy optimized pharmacophore approach is a versatile method for virtual screening. It is a type of structure based drug designing technique [21]. Potential pharmacophore was generated from ligand- JAK1 receptor docked complex and checked for the pharmacophore matching of JAK1 selective compounds.

***In vitro* studies on JAK1 selective ligand system**

Materials for in-vitro assay

JNK activity assay kit, Kinase star purchased from Ray Biotech, Inc, **raw264.7 cells** was procured from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India and maintained Dulbecos modified Eagles medium (Gibco, Invitrogen), MTT(Sigma, M-5655), compounds ellagic acid, cyanidin, quercetin , tofacitinib and dexamethasone were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

The experimental validation of JAK1 inhibitory activity of the candidates has been done through *in vitro* assay with the enzyme, JAK1. MTT assay[22] has been done on all the candidates to check their cytotoxicity towards 264.7 macrophage raw cells. Enzyme inhibition assay has been carried out by indirect ELISA method. Tofacitinib and dexamethasone, corticosteroid medicines were checked for their JAK1 inhibitory property and considered them as references for the JAK1 inhibitors. (Fig 1)

Fig 1: Flowchart for the methodology used in the study

Results and discussion

Molecular docking studies

The crystal structures of JAK family members are complexed with the FDA approved pan-JAK inhibitor tofacitinib. For ensuring the accuracy of docking calculations all the four JAK proteins were subjected to docking analysis with the crystal ligand.

The crystal ligand has furnished two types of hydrogen bonding interactions with hinge region residues of JAK1 enzyme; one with Glu957 and other with Leu959, one is hydrogen bond acceptor in nature while the other is showing donor effect at a distance of 2.28Å and 2.069Å respectively (Fig.2). The docking score of the corresponding system is -9.143. The distance of interactions is a factor governing the potential of interactions. The theory of hydrogen bonding explains that the distance for strong hydrogen bond lies in between 2.2 and 2.5 Å and a hydrogen bond having medium strength at a distance of 2.5 to 3.2 Å [23].

The crystal ligand has produced two types of interactions with JAK2 enzyme with the residues are Leu932 and Glu930 of hinge region and corresponding docking score is -9.121. (Fig.3). It furnished two hydrogen bonds with JAK3 through the hinge region residues Glu903 and Leu905 (Fig.4), with docking score is -9.87. Finally, the ligand has furnished 2 intermolecular interactions including side chain and end to end hydrogen bonding with residues Val981 and Glu979 of hinge region of TYK2 enzyme (Fig.5). The corresponding docking score is -8.956.

All these interactions are regarded as references for the detailed docking process. The ligand tofacitinib has bonded with all the JAK enzymes through their hinge region residues. This indicates that hinge region residues have to be considered for the virtual screening of JAK inhibitors. Tofacitinib has furnished high docking score with JAK3. The second interacting enzyme is JAK1. Both JAK3 and JAK1 are expressed in the IL4-JAK-STAT6 signaling pathway. Therefore, the interaction of tofacitinib with both JAK1 and JAK3 should be considered for a better virtual screening process of inhibitors capable of blocking the corresponding signaling pathway.

Docking studies with phytochemical system

To find out potential scaffolds having enhanced JAK1 inhibitory property 500 anti-inflammatory phytochemical compounds were taken for molecular docking studies. Low docking score (high negative value) has been exhibited by 17 compounds (near to the docking score of natural ligand – tofacitinib). The 17 final listed candidates were then subjected to docking analyses through extra precision mode with the JAK family members and checked their interactions (supplementary fig. S1).

It was found out that thymoquinone, apocynin, acetoxychavicol acetate, plumbagin, chalcone, ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin showed more affinity towards JAK3 and JAK1 which are capable of blocking the signaling pathway of IL4 by inhibiting JAK1 and JAK3 enzymes. Ellagic acid has produced a docking score of -10.27 with JAK1 and -10.21 with JAK3. Quercetin has shown a docking score -11.07 with JAK1 and -10.97 with JAK3. Both the candidates were furnished docking score lower than that of crystal ligand, tofacitinib (-9.007 for JAK1 and -9.87 for JAK3) Table 1, Table 2 and Fig. 6 shows the docking scores, binding energies and interactions of the phytochemicals with the JAK family members.

Table 1: Docking scores and binding energies of compounds with JAK isozymes

Compounds	Docking score				Binding Energy (kcal/mol)			
	JAK1	JAK2	JAK3	TYK2	JAK1	JAK2	JAK3	TYK2
Thymoquinone	-6.49	-5.90	-6.19	-6.02	-27.41	-34.59	-27.89	-30.15
Resveratrol	-6.74	-6.57	-8.28	-6.94	-31.69	-43.99	-41.90	-46.58
Apocynin	-7.28	-6.94	-7.24	-6.94	-34.15	-37.88	-39.07	-39.15
Acetoxy chavicol acetate	-6.46	-6.25	-6.48	-5.94	-29.89	-32.27	-36.58	-38.16
Plumbagin	-7.74	-7.51	-7.58	-6.87	-43.33	-40.67	-42.71	-41.92
Ascorbic acid	-5.94	-4.08	-5.37	-6.86	-6.89	-7.59	-14.13	-8.08
Chalcone	-6.85	-6.48	-6.75	-6.71	-36.60	-39.66	-45.58	-49.37
Quercetin	-11.06	-9.31	-10.97	-9.17	-49.69	-53.91	-51.60	-47.62
Ellagic acid	-10.27	-9.58	-10.21	-9.50	-58.41	-45.03	-50.17	-56.75
Cyanidin	-9.81	-9.77	-10.22	-9.44	-43.88	-46.67	-51.82	-52.75

Since the binding energies of all the compounds are highly negative it indicates that there is a huge release in energy during the formation of protein-ligand docked complexes and it can be inferred that all the docked complexes are energetically stabilized. Ascorbic acid-protein complex was not much stable in comparison with others. The candidates, ellagic acid quercetin and cyanidin have produced very low binding energy with JAK1 and JAK3.

Table 2: Hydrogen bonding interactions of the phytochemicals with the active site residues of the JAK family

Compound	Interactions with JAK1	Interactions with JAK2	Interactions with JAK3	Interactions with TYK2
Ellagic acid	Pro960, Leu959, Leu881, Gly1020	Leu932, Leu855, Gly993	Leu905, Ala966	Asp988, Val981, Gly1040
Quercetin	Glu957, Leu959, Asp1021	Glu930, Leu932, Leu855, Leu857	Leu905, Glu903, Leu828, Asn954	Asn1028, Glu979, Val981, Leu903
Cyanidin	Leu959, Pro960, Ser963, Glu966, Arg1007	Leu932, Glu930, Gly993, Asn981, Lys857	Lys830, Asn954, Ala966, Glu903, Leu905	Val981, Glu979, Gly1040, Asn1028

JAKs have two homology domains at the C-terminal end (residues 595–1154) consisting of eight α - helices, a kinase domain called JH1 and JH2 which is called pseudo kinase domain. JH1 is the catalytically active domain which is responsible for phosphorylation of tyrosine residues. JH2 binds the ATP but does not phosphorylate the substrates. The N-terminus (residues 865–958) comprising the β - sheets possess FERM domain and SH2-like domain which helps in the non-covalent attachment of JAKs to the tails of the cytokine receptors and stabilization of the structures for the activation of JH1 and JH2 domains[24] [6]. The amino acid side chains in and near the hinge region of JAK proteins play important roles in the regulation of kinase activity[25]. Thus targeting the ATP binding pocket in the JAK1 and the hinge region between JH2 and SH-2 line domain is crucial for JAK inhibition[26]. The hinge region consists of the residues Met956, Glu957, Phe958, Leu959, Pro960[24].

Ellagic acid formed hydrogen bonds with the hinge region residues Leu959 and Pro960. The hydroxyl groups showed interactions with the Leu881 of the β - sheet and the C-terminal α - helix active site Leu1020. Since the active site residues were the hydrogen bond donors to the ligand it might disturb the structure and stability of the α - helices of the C-terminus and hence change the active site and hinge region conformations leading to the obstruction in ATP binding for phosphorylation.

Quercetin furnished hydrogen bonds with Glu957 and Leu959 of the hinge region, and with Asp1021 of the C-terminus. It acted as hydrogen bond donor for all the interacting residues. Cyanidin showed interactions with the residues Leu959, Pro960, Ser963, Glu966 and Arg1007.

The high docking score and binding energy of ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin with both JAK1 and JAK3 have shed light on the inhibitory nature of the ligands to the IL4-JAK-STAT6 signaling pathway. The obstruction in ATP binding for phosphorylation due to the change in the active site and hinge region conformations shows that ellagic acid plays a major role in the inhibition JAK1 activity.

Pharmacophore generation from tofacitinib- JAK1 receptor complex

The structure based pharmacophoric feature was derived from the tofacitinib- JAK1 docked complex with the help of Glide extra precision mode docking.

E-pharmacophore suit was used for generating pharmacophoric feature hypothesis. Features are developed using Glide XP and docking post processing script. After calculating the scoring terms, a four-feature pharmacophore has been generated from the docking interaction. The feature comprises of a hydrogen bond acceptor (A), hydrogen bond donor (D) and two aromatic features. Interaction between nitrogen in the pyrimidine ring of ligand and NH₂ of Leu959 generated the hydrogen bond acceptor feature, interaction between NH of pyrrole ring in the ligand and C=O group of Glu957 has generated the hydrogen bond donor feature and aromaticity of both pyrimidine ring and pyrrole ring stands for aromatic feature in the pharmacophore (fig. 7 and table 3).

Table 3: Pharmacophore feature values

Rank	Feature	Score value	Pharmacophore Type	name
1	D5	-2.18	D	PhobEnPairHB+HBond
2	A2	-1.87	A	PhobEnPairHB+HBond
3	R10	-0.93	R	RingChemscoreHphobe
4	R9	-0.9	R	RingChemscoreHphobe

Pharmacophore matching of JAK1 selective compounds

Molecules which interact with JAK1 were subjected to pharmacophore matching with the pharmacophore feature ADRR using the Phase module of Schrodinger suit.

Table4: Pharmacophore score values of compounds with derived features

No.	Candidate	No. site matches	Matched ligand sites	Align score	Vector score	Volume score	Fitness score
1	Ellagic acid	4	A(2) D(5) R(9) R(10)	0.481400	0.880245	0.436296	1.915374
2	Quercetin	4	A(2) D(11) R(13) R(14)	0.793672	0.961146	0.339230	1.638983
3	Cyanidin	4	A(1) D(7) R(14) R(13)	1.192319	0.534579	0.308395	0.849375

Pharmacophore matching of JAK1 active compounds with the pharmacophoric features of tofacitinib have revealed (Table 4) that ellagic acid; quercetin and cyanidin are showing resemblance with the pharmacophoric features (fig. 8). Among them, ellagic acid has shown the highest resemblance with the features. Ellagic acid has a fused ring structure which is almost similar to the crystal ligand whose scaffold is also planar. Quercetin and cyanidin has a benzene ring singly bonded to the chromene scaffold due to which C-C rotation is possible. Quercetin and cyanidin differs only in the presence of an extra keto group in the chromene structure. This has made significant difference the fitness score between them. The keto substituted chromene group in quercetin is almost similar to that of ellagic acid which makes the substituents in the aromatic regions almost planar. Even though the compounds are not structurally similar with the crystal ligand, they are able to show the biological property of ligand due to the pharmacophore matching. From fig 9 it can be seen that the pharmacophore ADRR almost aligns with Ellagic acid and quercetin. The chromene ring, keto and hydroxy substituents are in right positions so as to make up the required pharmacophore. While in quercetin neither of them aligns properly Thus, under this point of view, potential of ellagic acid as a good JAK1 inhibitor has been explored.

MTT assay

The cell viable concentration of JAK1 selective candidates such as ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin along with the crystal ligand, tofacitinib were determined by MTT assay. (Table 5)

Table 5: Cell viable concentrations of compounds

Candidate	Concentration (($\mu\text{g/mL}$))	Percentage viability	Average Optical density	LD 90 value ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Tofacitinib	Control	100	0.4371	4.81425
	6.25	63.81	0.2789	
	12.5	44.41	0.1941	
	25	36.28	0.1586	
	50	35.06	0.1533	

	100	34.49	0.1508	
Ellagic acid	Control	100.0	0.4264	2.686
	6.25	73.86	0.3688	
	12.5	68.15	0.3403	
	25	68.23	0.3407	
	50	57.62	0.2877	
	100	49.92	0.2493	
Quercetin	Control	100.0	0.4993	1.44
	6.25	83.67	0.4178	
	12.5	75.43	0.3766	
	25	66.47	0.3319	
	50	62.87	0.3139	
	100	60.58	0.3025	
Cyanidin	Control	100.0	0.4993	11.1025
	6.25	93.75	0.4681	
	12.5	88.92	0.4440	
	25	88.44	0.4416	
	50	79.61	0.3975	
	100	67.27	0.3359	

Fig10: Percentage viability of Raw 264.7 cells varies with the concentration of samples

The percentage viability of **264.7 cells** by treating it with all JAK1 active compounds such as ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin were studied and compared the cell survival with that of tofacitinib, one of the approved drugs showing JAK1 inhibitory activity. It is clear that all the candidates considered here are showing minimum cell toxicity than tofacitinib towards **264.7 cells**. Among the selected candidates, cyanidin, one of the members of the flavonoid family has produced very good cell viability with **264.7 cells** at 11.103 µg/mL. LD90 is the lethal dose of a compound with the cell. LD90 stands for maximum cell viability (90% cell viability) that a compound can make with the cells at its minimum concentration. All the compounds mentioned here are exhibiting LD90 values closer to that of tofacitinib. Ellagic acid and quercetin are produced LD90 at concentrations 2.686 and 1.44 µg/mL respectively. Tofacitinib has produced LD90 of 4.81 µg/mL. Cyanidin exhibited cell safety even at higher concentration. This indicates the less toxic nature of cyanidin over other candidates. But as concentration increases, cell toxicity produced by the compounds increases (fig.9).

Protein inhibition assay

The compounds which show interaction with JAK1 protein such as ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin were subjected to JAK1 inhibition assay by indirect ELISA method. All the above said compounds at their LD90 concentration were incubated with LPS induced macrophage cells (264.7 cells). For ELISA, Janus Kinase enzyme specific antibody was taken as primary antibody and after the addition of secondary antibody; proper time has been provided for incubation and found out the concentration of compounds sustained in the cell corresponding to the Janus Kinase antibody. Tofacitinib and dexamethasone are taken as reference for the study. Both are checked for JAK1 inhibitory activity (Table 6).

Table6: JAK1 inhibition concentration and inhibitory activity of compounds

Compound	Activity concentration	Optical density	Concentration/ mg protein	% Activity
Control		1.2226	1.7887	73.69
Ellagic acid	2.686 µg/mL (8.8µM)	0.3689	0.4307	75.91
Quercetin	1.44 µg/mL (4.76 µM)	0.4847	0.5157	71.16
Cyanidin	11.1025µg/mL (0.38 µM)	0.4319	0.5458	69.48
Tofacitinib	112nM (0.112µM)	0.6883	0.6883	87.10
Dexamethasone	76nM(0.076µM)	0.5786	0.5786	89.15

Fig11: Graphical interpretation of JAK1 inhibitory concentration / inhibitory activity of compounds

The standard drugs, dexamethasone and tofacitinib have produced very high JAK1 inhibition at concentrations 0.076 and 0.112µM respectively (fig. 10). Dexamethasone is a popular corticosteroid used as an anti-inflammatory drug for asthma. Tofacitinib is another drug used as a JAK1 inhibitor for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. Many studies have been reported elucidating the anti-asthmatic activity of tofacitinib [27], [28]. Among the drugs, dexamethasone has shown highest JAK1 inhibitory activity at 0.076 µM.

Cyanidin has furnished high JAK1 inhibitory activity at very low concentration (0.38 µg/mL). But ellagic acid and quercetin have shown JAK1 inhibitory property at high concentration. This indicates that JAK1 inhibitory property of cyanidin is better than that of the other two. The MM-GBSA binding energy of the candidates, ellagic acid, quercetin, cyanidin, and tofacitinib obtained from molecular docking studies are compared with in-vitro JAK1 inhibitory activities and there exist a linear relationship between them.

Table7: Binding energy comparison with JAK1 inhibitory concentration

Candidate	MM-GBSA BE (kcal/mol)	JAK1 inhibitory property (in-vitro assay)
Tofacitinib	-58.86	87.1
Dexamethasone	-54.75	89.15
Ellagic acid	-58.66	75.91
Quercetin	-49.69	71.16
Cyanidin	-43.88	69.48

The graphical plot indicates that as the stability of the docked complex increases, percentage inhibition with the target also increases (Table 7, fig. 11). Therefore, binding energy is a function of inhibitory property of the ligand. This shed light on the affinity of the listed compounds towards the target, JAK1. Binding affinity of ellagic acid with JAK1 is very close to that of tofacitinib and dexamethasone and others are comparable. This indicates the stability of corresponding docked complex. All the reported concentrations are produced above 50% activity which is highly appreciable.

CONCLUSION

Molecular docking studies are a highly recommended *in silico* screening method for the drug designing scenario. High throughput virtual screening methods of Glide module has been utilized to find out highly interacting phytochemical compounds from a collection of 500 compounds. 17 compounds have been recognized as JAK1 inhibitors. They were further subjected to detailed docking studies using the extra precision mode of Glide module. Their affinity towards both JAK1 and JAK3 has also been realized by comparing the docking results of all JAK family isozymes with them. Structure based pharmacophore analysis has recognized the functional group similarity of ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin with the pharmacophore feature derived from the tofacitinib- JAK1 docked complex. Since both JAK1 and JAK3 are highly expressed in the IL4 driven JAK- STAT pathway for asthma, the compounds having high docking score with JAK1 and JAK3 alone have been considered for invitro assay with JAK1 enzyme by indirect ELISA method. Cytotoxicity studies have revealed the non-toxic effect of cyanidin, ellagic acid and quercetin towards themacrophage raw cells (264.7 cells). Among the compounds, cyanidin is found to be less toxic with the macrophage raw cells. The JAK1 inhibitory response of ellagic acid, quercetin and cyanidin are comparable with that of reference drugs, tofacitinib and dexamethasone. On comparing the activity / concentration of the entire candidates with the reference drugs, it has beenfound that cyanidin is a potential inhibitor than the other two compounds.

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Fig. 2: Docking interactions of tofacitinib with JAK1

Fig. 3: Docking interactions of tofacitinib with JAK2

Fig. 4: Docking interactions of JAK3 with tofacitinib

Fig. 5: Docking interactions of tofacitinib with TYK2 system

Fig. 6: 2D interaction diagrams of (a) ellagic acid (b) quercetin (c) cyanidin with JAK1

Fig.7: JAK1-ligand (tofacitinib) complex with pharmacophore (ADRR) (A-hydrogen bond acceptor, D-hydrogen bond donor, R- aromaticity)

Fig.8: Compounds with pharmacophore feature matching

Fig. 9: Compounds with aligned with pharmacophore features

Fig 12: JAK1 binding energy VS invitro inhibitory concentration of compounds